

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT COLLISION ON SELF-EFFICACY OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

Dr. Preeti Sharma* & Jayakala M**

* Professor, Faculty of social Science and Humanities, Mansarovar Global University, Madhya Pradesh

** Research Scholar, Faculty of Social Science and Humanities, Mansarovar Global University, Madhya Pradesh

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Abstract:

'The education of children depends upon schools, their organisational climate, curriculum and the teachers', which hints that the destiny of India is being shaped in her classrooms. Teachers have a vital role to play in the progress and development of the country. The teaching-learning process and class activities require a creative pursuit on the part of the teachers. New problems and new opportunities constantly arise which cannot be solved unless the teachers are equipped with the skill of classroom management. So, the classroom should be well managed and maintained to bring about a healthy learning environment. Classes are the sub-organizations where the objectives of education become more visible to students. Changing student behaviour, which is the target of education, takes place. The quality of educational administration is largely dependent upon the quality of Class management. This study performed a meta-analysis and research synthesis of the Impact of Classroom management on Self-efficacy of higher secondary school students.

Key Words: Classroom Management Collision, Self-Efficacy.

Classroom Management:

Classroom management is the process of enhancing the learning environment, physical interaction between teachers and students, student to student, parents and others, stimulating and motivating children to learn, control and supervision throughout the school to facilitate and encourage cooperation in teaching and learning activities in the classroom smoothly, will as a result, improve the quality of students' performance (Wisetrinthong, Sirisuthi and Weangsamoot, 2012). Classroom management includes all the actions teachers take to create and maintain an environment conducive to learning (Brophy, 2006). By this term the investigator means the higher secondary school teachers' ability to manage time, space, resources and students' behaviours and creating a climate that encourages students learning.

Self-Efficacy:

Self-efficacy is the belief that an individual has control over his self and is able to execute a behaviour, it is the extent to which an individual believes that they can master a particular skill. An individual's level of self-efficacy is a tool to know how well a person makes an attempt in his activities. The level of self-efficacy determines the ability to attain desired goals. This is the main determinant for cognitive, motivational, affective and decision-making processes. The success in the performance of an individual is determined by the self-efficacy and its impact on a person's choice of behaviour and motivation.

Objective of the Study:

To find out the significant impact of Classroom management on the Self-efficacy of higher secondary students for the whole sample and subsamples based on Subject Specialization (Humanities/ Commerce/ Science)

Methodology:

The method adopted should always be valid, reliable and appropriate to the nature of the problem under investigation and the kind of data that the problem demands. The present study aims to find out the impact of Classroom management on Self-efficacy. For getting a clear picture of the scenario of the problem; it was intended to collect extensive and true representative data. Hence normative survey method will be adopted by the investigator for collecting the data.

Variables of the Study:

The independent variable used for the present study is Classroom Management Impact the dependent variables used for the present study is Self-efficacy. The Classificatory variables in this study is Subject Specialization (Humanities/ Commerce/ Science)

Sample for the Study:

A sample of 400 High school students will be selected using stratified random sampling technique giving due representation to the classificatory variables.

Tools for the Study:

The tools used for the collection of the data are: Classroom management impact scale and Self-efficacy scale

Statistical Techniques Employed:

The statistical techniques used for analyzing the data are the descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, and standard deviation were employed to know the nature of distribution and to find the level of variables. Karl Pearson’s Coefficient of Correlation is used to find out the nature of the impact of independent variables on dependent variables.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant correlation between Classroom management Impact and Self-efficacy among higher secondary school students for the total sample

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom management and Self-efficacy of higher secondary school students are analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among them. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 1.

Table 1: Correlation between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy among higher secondary school students for total sample

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
Classroom Management Impact	400	150.95	25.39	0.537	0.001
Self-Efficacy	400	44.92	5.78		

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.537 indicates that there is a moderately strong positive relationship between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy variables. As Classroom management impact scores increase, the Self-efficacy scores tend to increase as well, and vice versa. The p-value of 0.001 suggests that this correlation is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.01. In summary, this correlation analysis suggests that there is a significant positive association between classroom management skills and self-efficacy levels among the participants in this study. Higher levels of classroom management impact tend to be associated with higher levels of self-efficacy in the observed population. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom management and Self-efficacy among higher secondary school students for the total sample is rejected.

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy of higher secondary school students are graphically presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy among higher secondary school students on total samples

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant correlation between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy of higher secondary students with regard to Humanities specialization

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy were analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among the Humanities groups of higher secondary students. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 2.

Table 2: Correlation between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy among higher secondary students with regard to Humanities specialization

Subject Specialization	Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
Humanities	Classroom Management Impact	140	152.10	22.87	0.479	0.001
	Self-Efficacy	140	46.21	5.71		

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.479 indicates that there is a moderate positive relationship between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy variables. As Classroom management impact scores in the Humanities specialization increase, the Self-efficacy scores in the same group tend to increase as well, and vice versa. The p-value of 0.001 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.01. In conclusion, the correlation analysis indicates that there is a significant positive association between classroom management impact and self-efficacy levels among individuals with a Subject Specialization in Humanities. Those who excel in classroom management impact within the Humanities specialization also tend to have higher self-efficacy levels, and vice versa. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom management and Self-efficacy among the higher secondary school students with Humanities Subject Specialization is rejected.

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy of Humanities Subject Specialization students are graphically presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy with regard to Humanities students

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant correlation between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy of higher secondary students with regard to Science specialization

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom management and Self-efficacy were analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among Science subject specialization groups of higher secondary school students. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 3.

Table 3: Correlation between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy among higher secondary students with regard to Science Specialization

Subject Specialization	Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
Science	Classroom Management Impact	140	152.89	28.47	0.607	0.001
	Self-Efficacy	140	43.36	6.01		

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.607 indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy variables. As Classroom management impact scores in the Science specialization increase, the Self-efficacy scores in the same group tend to increase as well, and vice versa. This suggests that individuals specializing in Science who demonstrate better classroom management impact also tend to have higher levels of self-efficacy. The p-value of 0.001 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.01. In conclusion, the correlation analysis indicates that there is a significant positive association between classroom management impact and self-efficacy levels among individuals with a Subject Specialization in Science. Those who excel in classroom management impact within the Science specialization also tend to have higher self-efficacy levels, and vice versa. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom management and Self-efficacy of the higher secondary school students with Science Subject Specialization is rejected.

Mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy of Science Specialization students are graphically presented in figure 3.

Figure 3: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy of higher secondary students with regard to Science Specialization

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant correlation between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy of higher secondary students with regard to Commerce Specialization

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy were analysed to find out whether any significant correlation exists among Commerce Subject Specialization groups of higher secondary school students. The data and results of the correlation analysis are given in the table 4.28.

Table 4: Correlation between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy among higher secondary students with Commerce specialization students

Subject Specialization	Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
Commerce	Classroom Management Impact	120	147.34	24.16	0.581	0.001
	Self-Efficacy	120	45.24	5.19		

The positive correlation coefficient of 0.581 indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy variables. As Classroom management impact scores in the Commerce specialization increase, the Self-efficacy scores in the same group tend to increase as well, and vice versa. This suggests that individuals specializing in Commerce who demonstrate better classroom management impact also tend to have higher levels of self-efficacy. The p-value of 0.001 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.01. In conclusion, the correlation analysis indicates that there is a significant positive association between classroom management impact and self-efficacy levels among individuals with a Subject Specialization in Commerce. Those who excel in classroom management impact within the Commerce specialization also tend to have higher self-efficacy levels, and vice versa. Hence the hypothesis stated that, there is no significant correlation between Classroom management and Self-efficacy among higher secondary school students with Commerce Subject Specialization is rejected

The mean and standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy of Commerce specialization students are graphically presented in figure 4

Figure 4: Mean and Standard deviation scores of Classroom management impact and Self-efficacy among Commerce specialization students

Educational Implications of the Study:

The present study is undertaken to find out the impact of Classroom management on Self-efficacy of higher secondary students. The classificatory variable selected is Subject Specialization which considered for the categorization of subsamples. The investigator analysed the significant relationship between the Classroom management Impact and Self-efficacy. The findings of the study throw light on the fact that there should be an impact of Classroom management on students on Self-efficacy. So the code of Classroom management which have to be strictly follow by the teaching community for the proper development of Self-efficacy among students. The school teachers have to aware about the Classroom management techniques and acquire the necessary teaching skill to enhance the Self-efficacy of students. The future of the children is quite safe in the hands of al skilled teacher; on the other hand if a teacher suffers from lack of classroom management techniques, he is not only harming himself but doing a great harm to the children under his supervision and to the society at large. The findings of the study have profound implications for Teachers, Teacher Educators, Research Agencies, Research Scholars, Curriculum Constructors, Course Designers, and Professional Training Institution. Some of the implications of the study are:

- Teachers should aware about the importance of different Class management techniques and its application in the field of Teaching - learning processes.
- Parents and teachers should provide proper opportunities for their children to attain high degree of Self-efficacy to face the obstacles in their future life
- The government and school authorities should arrange some in-service training to teachers to increase their Classroom management skills.
- Teachers should become able in managing the classroom activities and putting his maximum effort to provide a better classroom climate to strengthen the students Self efficacy.
- Make aware about the importance of Class management techniques to become a good teacher, especially in this present social scenario.
- Inculcate the positive attitude among teachers to face the challenges in the field of classroom management strategy.
- Teachers make aware their students about the importance of Self-efficacy for the successful completion of education in this highly competitive preset world.
- In-service and pre-service courses should be periodically revise and provide importance to study the classroom management strategies for school teachers

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